

Change of Sensible Shades in Literary Translation: a Study Through the Work of F. Dostoevsky

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the study of changes in meaning and the transformation of punctuation in literary translation. It explores the concept of literary translation, presents examples from Fyodor Dostoevsky's work *Crime and Punishment*, and provides general conclusions on the topic.

Keywords: literary translation, technical translation, punctuation, literary device.

Introduction

Literary translation is the process of translating literary works, such as novels, short stories, poetry, plays, and other creative texts, from one language to another. The primary goal of literary translation is to preserve the style, tone, atmosphere, and emotions of the original text while conveying them in the target language. This is not merely a technical process but a true art, requiring a deep understanding of the culture, language, and literary techniques involved.

Literary translation allows readers around the world to become familiar with works of literature written in different languages, facilitating the exchange of cultural values and enriching global literature. Literary translation stands apart from other types of translation due to its unique characteristics and specific features that are not found in other translation areas.

Comparing Technical and Literary Translation

To better understand literary translation, it is useful to compare it with technical translation. In technical translation, there is a high degree of repetition in words, which results in more automated translation processes. Technical translators often use Computer-Assisted Translation (CAT) systems, which are tools that remember and re-use recurring text segments.

In recent years, the quality of machine translation, such as *Google Translate*, has greatly improved. However, while technical texts may benefit from the assistance of such tools, literary translators must rely solely on their linguistic intuition, knowledge, and creativity. A literary translator makes new linguistic decisions each time they work on a text.

Definition of Literary Translation

Literary translation is a unique form of literary creation that involves the recreation of a text in one language using the tools of another. The translator of literary prose does not merely "photograph" the original; they recreate it creatively. To be a translator, it is not enough to simply know a foreign language; a translator is an artist, a master of words, and a co-creator in the artistic work of the author they are translating. They are as much a servant of the arts as an actor, sculptor, or painter. The original text serves as the material for their complex and often inspired creative process.

The Role of Idioms and Figurative Language in Translation

In the translations of Dostoevsky's works, the nuanced meanings the author wishes to convey are often expressed through phraseology and idiomatic expressions. For example, in *Crime and Punishment*, the author uses the phrase:

"...Она была из деревенских баб и очень болтливая баба (кухарка единственная служанка хозяйкина)..." (Dostoevsky, *Crime and Punishment*, p. 30).

In this passage, the adjective *болтливый* (talkative) is translated into Uzbek as someone who talks a lot and cannot keep secrets, translated as "**vaysaqi**". Ibrohim G'afurov, the Uzbek translator, uses a different idiomatic expression: "**elakka chiqsa ellik og'iz gapiradiganlar xilidan edi**," which can be literally translated as "If she went to the sieve, she would talk fifty mouths." While this retains the meaning of excessive talking, the metaphor is distinctly Uzbek, and the meaning of the original phrase becomes more colorful and culturally specific.

Another example can be seen in the expression: "**Денег не платишь и с фатеры не сходишь**" (p. 29), translated as "**Ijara haqini to'lamas emishsan, buning ustiga dimog'ing baland emish**" (p. 37). The idiomatic expression "не сходить с фатеры" (literally "not leaving the apartment") is translated as "**dimog'ing baland**" (literally "your nose is high" in Uzbek), adding a local flavor while maintaining the essence of the original meaning. Here, the metaphorical image is adapted to suit Uzbek cultural expressions, thereby enriching the text's imagery.

Punctuation and Meaning in Literary Translation

Punctuation in literary texts is also crucial for maintaining the intended meaning and emotional tone. For example, Dostoevsky's use of punctuation, such as dashes and exclamation marks, contributes to the intensity and emotional impact of his dialogues. In translations, this punctuation may sometimes need to be adjusted to match the syntactical and emotional flow of the target language.

Consider this passage from *Crime and Punishment*, where the word "**вон**" (meaning "there") is used:

"...Как ты смеешь, говорю, с проданным локтем ко мне входить, – вон, негодяй!" (Dostoevsky, *Crime and Punishment*, p. 1959).

This is translated into Uzbek as:

"**Mening oldimga qanday qilib tirsagi yirtiq koylakda kirishga jurat etding, qani, lanati, bir tuyogingni shiqqillatib qol bu yerdan!**"

In this case, "**вон**" becomes the more detailed expression "**qani, la`nati**" ("damn you"), which not only conveys the intended tone but also adapts the expression to the specific cultural context.

Conclusion

From the above examples, it is clear that literary translation involves not only a direct, literal translation but also an imaginative understanding of the author's intent. The translator adds their own vision of the work while ensuring they do not stray from the original text. This creative process makes literary translation a form of artistic collaboration between the original author and the translator, and it allows for the rich, nuanced shades of meaning to be conveyed across languages. The translator's task is to find the most appropriate ways to maintain the integrity of the original text while adapting it to the cultural and linguistic specifics of the target language.

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